

UNIVERSALIZATION OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: BETWEEN DISCOURSES AND ACTIONS IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF CAETITÉ/BAHIA

UNIVERSALIZACIÓN DE LA EDUCACIÓN INCLUSIVA: ENTRE DISCURSOS Y ACCIONES
EN EL MUNICIPIO DE CAETITÉ/BAHIA

UNIVERSALIZAÇÃO DA EDUCAÇÃO INCLUSIVA: ENTRE DISCURSOS E AÇÕES NO
MUNICÍPIO DE CAETITÉ/BAHIA

Cymone Martins Cotrim Teixeira ¹
Sandra Márcia Campos Pereira ²

Manuscript received on: May 30, 2023.

Approved on: April 15, 2024.

Published on: May 24, 2024.

Abstract

This article is part of a broader research entitled “The Universalization of Inclusive Education in the Municipal Education Plan of Caetité-Bahia: problematizing discourses and actions” and is based on the analysis of discourses on the universalization of inclusive education in goal 4 of the Municipal Plan of Education (PME) in Caetité-BA. We take as a theoretical-methodological basis the theories and postulates of the French philosopher Michel Foucault, with the devices of knowledge, power and governmentality, to reflect on the process of constitution of discourses. Data was produced from interviews, questionnaires and document analysis. Three subjects who are part of the PME implementation were interviewed and three subjects representing Special and Inclusive Education in the Municipal Education Forum answered the questionnaire. The results point to a desire for truth to expand access in the inclusive perspective of students with disabilities to common education from the PME; as for the materialization of the strategies of the PME goal 4, the analysis shows a lack of knowledge or clarity of knowledge in the field of inclusive education, for the exercise of this knowledge; the actions proposed for the implementation of the PME goal 4 reveal themselves to be inconsistent in the context of schooling.

Keywords: Universalization of education; Educational inclusion; Municipal Education Plan.

Resumen

Este artículo forma parte de una investigación más amplia titulada “La universalización de la educación inclusiva en el Plan Municipal de Educación de Caetité-Bahia: problematizando discursos y acciones” y se basa en el análisis de los discursos sobre la universalización de la educación inclusiva en el objetivo 4 del Plan Municipal. Plan de Educación (PME) de Caetité-BA. Tomamos como base teórico-metodológica las teorías y postulados del filósofo francés Michel

¹ Doctoral student and Master in Teaching at the State University of Southwest Bahia. Member of the Research Group on Basic Education Policy and Management. Member of the Network of Researchers on Special Education Financing.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3677-5102> Contact: cymonecotrim@gmail.com

² Doctorate in School Education from São Paulo State University. Professor in the Postgraduate Program in Teaching at the State University of Southwest Bahia. Coordinator of the Basic Education Policy and Management Research Group.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8811-3680> Contact: sandra.campos@uesb.edu.br.

Foucault, con los dispositivos de conocimiento, poder y gubernamentalidad, para reflexionar sobre el proceso de constitución de los discursos. Los datos se produjeron a partir de entrevistas, cuestionarios y análisis de documentos. Se entrevistaron tres sujetos que forman parte de la implementación del PME y tres sujetos representantes de la Educación Especial e Inclusiva en el Foro Municipal de Educación respondieron el cuestionario. Los resultados apuntan a un deseo de verdad para ampliar el acceso en la perspectiva inclusiva de los estudiantes con discapacidad a la educación común desde el PME; en cuanto a la materialización de las estrategias de la meta 4 del PME, el análisis muestra una falta de conocimiento o claridad de conocimiento en el ámbito de la educación inclusiva, para el ejercicio de estos conocimientos; las acciones propuestas para la implementación del objetivo 4 del PME se revelan inconsistentes en el contexto de la escolarización.

Palabras clave: Universalización de la educación; Inclusión educativa; Plan Municipal de Educación.

Resumo

Este artigo é parte de uma pesquisa mais ampla intitulada “A Universalização da Educação Inclusiva no Plano Municipal de Educação de Caetité-Bahia: problematizando discursos e ações” e fundamenta-se na análise dos discursos sobre a universalização da educação inclusiva na meta 4 do Plano Municipal de Educação (PME) em Caetité-BA. Tomamos como base teórico-metodológica teorias e postulados do filósofo francês Michel Foucault, com os dispositivos de saber, poder e governamentalidade, para refletir sobre o processo de constituição dos discursos. Os dados foram produzidos a partir de entrevistas, questionários e análise documental. Foram entrevistados três sujeitos que fazem parte da implementação do PME e responderam ao questionário três sujeitos representantes da Educação Especial e Inclusiva no Fórum Municipal de Educação. Os resultados apontam para uma vontade de verdade de ampliar o acesso na perspectiva inclusiva dos alunos com deficiência ao ensino comum a partir do PME; quanto à materialização das estratégias da meta 4 do PME, a análise evidencia uma falta de conhecimento ou clareza de um saber no campo da educação inclusiva, para o exercício desses saberes; as ações propostas para implementação da meta 4 do PME revelam-se inconsistentes no contexto da escolarização.

Palavras-chave: Universalização da educação; Inclusão educacional; Plano Municipal de Educação.

Introduction

The following discussions took into account the identification and analysis of actions to materialize inclusive education in the municipality of Caetité-BA, according to the articulation between access and ‘continuous service’. This text is part of the analyzes carried out in the research entitled “The Universalization of Inclusive Education in the Municipal Education Plan of Caetité-Bahia: problematizing discourses and actions” and is based on the analysis of discourses on the universalization of inclusive education in goal 4 of the Plan Municipal Education Council (PME) in Caetité-BA and the actions to

materialize these speeches. In this study, access is qualified not only by mandatory enrollment, but by remaining in pedagogical learning conditions that promote teaching with equity, respecting diversity. The 'continuum' service is characterized by support for the schooling of the target student of special education, in a complementary or supplementary way, characterized by a support network, involving professionals, resources and specific services to meet the specificity of each subject. In our view, support services are conditions for the materialization of the discourse of universalization of inclusive education in the context of common schools.

The purpose of analyzing the statement 'universalization' is to understand its genealogy, completing the conceptions that subjectify knowledge, in addition to identifying the positioning, actions and discourses involved in them to establish their materialization in goal 4 of the PME in the municipality of Caetité- BA (2015-2025). In this way, the knowledge produced about the universalization of inclusive education constitutes a space for the production of discourse and its distribution among subjects and their place of speech.

Thus, the research aims to contribute to the field of knowledge of Inclusive Education and public policies for a critical reflection on the distances between the discourses of universalization of education and the actions implemented to significantly favor access for the target audience of education. special education to common education.

For the organization and presentation of the analyzed data, we chose to divide it into two axes of analysis: The context of materialization of the PME: an articulation between access and services and The PME in the subjects' speeches: actions and conceptions.

We highlight that the results presented do not intend to point out what is true or false, but rather the policies that govern and govern these discourses and that in a network of knowledge, power and governmentality build their contradictions and meanings. We understand that the policies that govern are not limited to the notion of administrative power, to the fact that it is led by the other, but to think about public policies, “[...] between the government of oneself and the government of the other, this hesitation between the obedience of being led by the other and the construction of oneself [...]” (Resende, 2018, p. 216), and its space of action.

Methodology

We take as a theoretical-methodological basis the theorizations and postulates of the French philosopher Michel Foucault, as his contribution is based on devices and propositions around knowledge, the exercise of power and governmentality to reflect on the process of constituting discourses.

Given the relevance of governmentality in the analysis undertaken in this text, we highlight the meaning it gains as “[...] more or less reflected and calculated modes of action, but all destined to act on the possibilities of action of other individuals” (Foucault, 1995, p. 247). From this perspective, governmentality defines the control and modeling of subjects and their social conduct through different techniques for creating governable subjects; To this end, it adds biopower, which is identified by two principles: the technology of discipline and the technology of biopolitics. The exercise of power is, therefore, linked, in biopower, to the discipline of the body and manipulation of subjects to make them docile and useful; and, in another aspect, in biopolitics, as it focuses on the life of a population, controls events, manages social risks, produces mass effects (Foucault, 2010).

Data were produced through interviews, questionnaires and document analysis. Three subjects who are part of the implementation of the PME were interviewed and three subjects representing Special and Inclusive Education at the Municipal Education Forum responded to the questionnaire. Considering the place of speech, enunciators will be characterized with the letter (L) followed by a number.

The context of PME materialization: a link between access and service

The city of Caetité in Bahia state, in compliance with the prerogatives of Article 8 of law 13.005/2014, which approves the PNE, carries out evaluation and updating of the Municipal Education Plan (PME) under Law No. 789, of June 22, 2015 Guiding educational policy for the next 10 years, the PME complies with the National Education Guidelines and Bases Law, Federal Law No. 9394/96, in accordance with the PNE guidelines and goals.

The strategies of goal 4 of the PME in the studied municipality are distributed according to the specificities of service and, in this way, reveal the inclusive knowledge undertaken in its construction. Access is provided for the population aged 4 (four) to 17 (seventeen) years old, the age group for compulsory schooling, and also for children aged 0 (zero) to 3 (three) years old, as confirmed in strategy 4.2, which aims to

[...] to promote, within the term of this Plan, the universalization of school assistance to the demand manifested by families of children aged 0 (zero) to 3 (three) years old with disabilities, pervasive developmental disorders and high abilities/giftedness, observing the which provides for Law No. 9,394, of December 20, 1996 (Caetité, 2015).

In order to expand the debate on the universalization discourse and the actions to materialize this discourse, as a condition of the will to truth eligible in the PME, to subsidize the implementation of the universalization of inclusive education in the municipality of Caetité, we propose a visualization in Chart 1, below, which identifies the proportion of schools that indicate in their network the existence of students with disabilities included in the education networks.

Chart 1 - Students included in the perspective of Inclusive Education in the municipality - Enrollment Data census/2018.

Administrative Dependency	Total number of students enrolled
City	251
State	24
Private	20

Source: Directorate of Educational Statistics (DEEP). National Institute of Educational Studies and Research Anísio Teixeira (INEP). Ministry of Education (MEC) (2018).

As we can see the data in Chart 1, the materialization of goal 4 and strategy 4.2 can be glimpsed in the presence of target audience students in special education in teaching units in the municipality of Caetité. We highlight, on a larger scale, the provision in the initial years in the municipal public network; in the state public network in Regular High School and Professional Education courses we observed a reduced demand, justified, in the case of Caetité, by the recent inclusion process, added to the difficulties of this public remaining in common classes due to the lack of resources and services suitable for your learning. We continue to demonstrate, through the data in Chart 2, below, that in the private network the number of students included is significant, if we consider the overall enrollment, which is 1,654 students, including daycare, preschool, elementary and high school.

City schools, in large numbers, receive target audience students for special education and this distribution occurs depending on the location of the schools, serving the urban area and different communities in the rural area, as per the distribution illustrated in the following table.

Chart 2 - Teaching Units of the Municipal network with students included - 2019 Enrollment.

TOTAL STUDENTS INCLUDED	TOTAL OF SCHOOLS	34
	URBAN AREA	176
	RURAL AREA	69
	TOTAL	245

Source: Produced by the researchers based on the enrollment chart per school in the Municipal Education network. According to Table 1. (DEEP/INEP). Ministry of Education (MEC) (2018).

According to previous data, the target audience of special education students included in common education in the municipal network of Caetité make up a total of 245 (two hundred and forty-five) students, 176 (one hundred and seventy-six) from the urban area and 69 (sixty-nine) from rural areas. Of this number of students, 120 (one hundred and twenty) present a report, that is, less than half, compared to the 125 (one hundred and twenty-five) who do not have a report attesting to some type of limitation and/or disability. However, we infer the existence of this last group of students, based on the interview with speaker L2, who states: “[...] we are in a universe of 7 thousand and so many students, of which there are 350, 120 with reports, so, like this, the growth in relation to this issue was very large [...]”; This statement refers to satisfaction with the number of students with medical or psychopedagogical reports. L1, in turn, informs:

[...] around 300 students, that is to say 250/300 more or less; It fluctuates a lot due to the census. So, the period that we are there closing the census is around 250, but we can serve up to 300 students in the network. In this year 2019 [...] (L1).

Based on these statements, the materiality of the discourse begins to emerge in actions that envision access for students, the target audience for special education, in the context of inclusive education. Student access to common schools is present in the strategies and is on the rise in previous speeches. However, it is possible to observe that speakers L1 and L2, when portraying in their interviews a record greater than that elucidated by the enrollment table, raise an interesting question: who are the students

without a report? We do not know. But we can assume that in a context of inclusion, students without a report will not receive adequate assistance for their specific needs, will not have access to the resources necessary for their learning and, consequently, will not have significant learning for their educational and social development.

This issue brings us closer to Foucault's postulate of Biopolitics, in which this new population (people with disabilities) is now understood as a new body, for which new knowledge is necessary. For Veiga-Neto (2001), the great novelty is the knowledge that deals with understanding the approximations, the differences, their regularities and from these establishing a collaboration that culminates in potential access to the common school, through a network of inclusion information and resources.

It is important to note that access is expressed in 2 (two) strategies, 4.2 and 4.3, which make up the statement strategies for promoting access to common education and which signal the universalization of access to common education for target students in special education. Paying attention to goal 4.3, this access occurs through an intersectoral partnership between health, social development and education, as expressed in the goal itself, to guarantee the identification and care of children who are too young to access schooling.

When analyzing the expansion of PME strategies according to the statement of services to be provided by area of service or specificity of disability, or developmental disorder, we observed, by way of example, that strategies 4.8, 4.9 and 4.10, despite being separate, deal with services for students with visual impairments, as we see in the following excerpt:

4.8. From the second year of validity of this plan, make available to blind students and those with low vision, spoken textbooks, in Braille, in enlarged characters and/or electronic media.

4.9. Ensure, from the validity of this plan, the presence of a Braille specialist with resources and equipment (computer, Braille printer and printing software) to prepare all school materials, necessary in school units, wherever there are, students with blindness.

4.10. Make available, from the validity of this plan, a computer suitable for student use in the classrooms of teaching units, where there are blind students or those with low vision (Caetité, 2015).

The services proposed in the strategies above refer to assistance to people with visual impairment (Low vision/low vision and Blindness), while service strategies 4.20, 4.22 and 4.30 correspond to the specific area of deafness and the services necessary for this population. If analyzed in depth, we will see that there would be no need for expansion, since the services complement each other. However, as our focus is on offering resources and services that favor service within the dynamics of PME strategies, these guarantee the provision of bilingual education, in Brazilian Sign Language (LIBRAS); LIBRAS teaching plans to prepare and approve, from the second year of PME's validity, a Bill to regulate the profession of auxiliary teacher and Libras interpreter, Libras translators and interpreters, interpreter-guides for the deaf-blind, teachers of Libras mainly deaf and bilingual teachers (Caetité, 2015). These services promote access for people with deafness to common education, as well as to cultural environments and social life, respecting the specificities of the deaf community.

In general, keeping due proportions in mind, the analysis of statements referring to services favors the understanding that the PME seeks to insert new knowledge that, in the ordering of bodies, overcomes the challenges of inclusive practice. In this sense, governmentality passes through this ordering of bodies, through access to a network of information that will direct the lives of subjects imbued with knowledge and with the guarantee “[...] of the progressive restructuring of the educational system of teaching aimed at for devising inclusion policies, ensuring that the target audience of special education recognizes their uniqueness, favoring their integral development and the construction of their autonomy”, according to strategy 4.4 (Caetité, 2015).

The services present in the PME strategies reveal a true desire to exercise inclusion and reinforce the offer of services in multifunctional resource rooms, as we can see in strategy 4.11, whose objective is “[...] to carry out continued training for professionals education, support and monitors for AEE, in urban and rural schools in the public education network”; and in strategy 4.14: “[...] the offer of Specialized Educational Assistance – AEE, in multifunctional resource rooms and/or specialized services, public or affiliated” (Caetité, 2015).

In time, it is important to highlight the reflections proposed by Mendes, Viralonga and Zerbato (2014, p. 28) “[...] on the current way in which multifunctional resource rooms spread across the country operate, whether they are in fact contributing to the school inclusion of students targeted by special education or if they are reinforcing a space of segregation”. According to the authors, when providing specialized educational assistance, offered exclusively in resource rooms, the conjecture that the impediment lies with the student and not in the school environment to receive them is reinforced.

By choosing these strategies in the PME as support for school inclusion in the municipality, a desire for truth is evident that directs towards the conquest of otherness, establishing the distinction between what provides opportunities and what does not, in order to build existential territories where differences are not indifferent or tolerated, but welcomed. However, the subjects' speeches, directly linked to the contexts in which the speeches of the PME strategies are implemented, in their positivity, oscillate between the desire for truth undertaken and the actions that characterize its implementation, as we present below.

The PME in the subjects' speeches: actions and conceptions

The materialization of discourses on the universalization of inclusive education, foreseen in the PME, is analyzed in the context of the practices that begin to be enunciated in the respondents' statements and aims to understand how they conceive the universalization of inclusive education through the discourses and actions implemented to materialize them.

With an emphasis on aspects about discourse from the perspective of Michel Foucault, we understand that “[...] the production of discourse is at the same time controlled, selected, organized and distributed by a certain number of procedures whose function is to configure its powers and dangers, to master its random event” (Foucault, 2010, p. 9). In short, no one is given the right to give a speech; it is not neutral, it is linked to the space of production and the place of speech of the subjects.

Thus, we selected some utterances already worked on in the previous sections as markers to guide the presentation and analysis of the speeches. From this perspective, the discourse on access is initially taken for analysis because it is the object of understanding of the research as a statement signaling universalization. The right to inclusive education is also guaranteed in the Brazilian Inclusion Law No. 13,146/2015, which in its art. 28 consolidates the right of people with disabilities to inclusive education. The document states that it is up to the public authorities to ensure, create, develop, implement, encourage, monitor and evaluate the improvement of educational systems, aiming to guarantee conditions of access, permanence, participation and learning through the provision of services and accessibility resources that eliminate barriers and promote full inclusion.

The universalization of access in the municipal context, according to statements by speakers L1 and L2, occurs amidst doubts and lack of knowledge, since, “[...] with the implementation of the Center, we had a new look at inclusive education in Caetité, several actions were strengthened, Caetité really needed the Center [...]”, highlights L1. For L2, the process takes place following the route:

(L2). [...] in fact, we started when we were little, this process of inclusive education is new to me. As these students arrived on the network, we looked for ways to provide this support, because it wasn't just access, but what we could offer so that this student could actually be included in the classroom, this was our biggest challenge [...] (L2).

[...] it is a flag [...], and the first pedagogical week was designed, planned, and was exactly about inclusion [...]. So, we bring these discussions and from then on, we begin to realize that the education department alone would not be able to ensure that the municipality had the range of services that we provided, right? (L2).

When looking back at the specialized service format, L1 and L2 compose a diagnostic statement from the period that precedes the preparation of the PME (2015-2025), while L3 states “[...] he is unaware of” any inclusion policy in the municipality before the Municipal Education Plan. Thus, based on the interviews, we understand that access is being considered as new subjects are incorporated into the reality of schools, contradicting the scientific discourse that foresees a change in the scope of the education system, school units and pedagogical practices to “[...] the reorganization of

the educational system with the review of old conceptions and educational paradigms, in the search to enable the cognitive, cultural and social development of these students, respecting their differences” (Garcia, 2007, p. 181).

It is verified that, with each speech of the subjects, as new knowledge is being constructed, new actions are being taken, “[...] the service was modified, the coordination was not able to cope, I have to reinforce this, as it was not meeting all the demand [...] it was becoming a school reinforcement [...]” (L1). This action is confirmed in L2's speech: “[...] we worked all the time with this coordination with specialist teachers, who were unable to meet all the disability demands that arrived on the network [...]”.

This diagnosis carried out by the management team in the face of new knowledge about inclusive education refers to the period that precedes the preparation of the PME (2015-2025) and provides a new tone for the inclusion policy of the municipal network, according to the interviews carried out with the responsible for managing municipal education.

What we did, there was no longer any special coordination, with specialist teachers, why? [...] a screening was carried out; these students were taken to the Center. [...] And we set up a new multidisciplinary team that has a different perspective on the network's service, and they can, in addition to providing this clinical service, also provide service and training for teachers, service and monitoring for parents and managers (L1).

That wasn't the service, it was a specialized service for that disability that the student had, and then we thought about how, that's when this team came now, a team of professionals who are providing this support. [...] (L2).

In the previous excerpt, L1's speech brings to reflection a new composition of services offered by the municipality, which are now clinical at the municipal level and educational-pedagogical at CEEEC at the state level. This change in the service format, while being based on a desire for truth about the best way to assist students with disabilities, can take the inclusive discourse in a different direction from that proposed. It is necessary to consider, as Skliar (1987, p. 26) mentions, “[...] what is the politics of signifiers and the representations that are produced and reproduced in this proposal”. In the words of L1, the work of specialized teachers is given up, “[...] there is no longer any special coordination, with specialist teachers [...]”, prioritizing clinical care.

Even so, there is a partnership with CEEEC, as confirmed in L3's speech, in two moments:

[...] currently does not have a special cooperative education. Students with disabilities are served by CEEEC and there is a multidisciplinary team, made up of a psychologist, a speech therapist and a psychopedagogue, from the municipal education department, who monitors these students (L3).

[...] Some CEEEC teachers, when traveling in regular schools, guide the management and pedagogical team on the need for the PPP to consider a special education policy from an inclusive perspective (L3).

Choosing clinical care as the only model in the municipal network, even if anchored by partners in other areas, may result in a biomedical model of inclusion. In this sense, the discourses diverge when electing in the PME the expansion of 'continuum' services in school units and teacher training and clinical support services.

The materiality of the discourse begins to emerge in the actions that envision access for students, the target audience for special education. The statement "service" is directly linked to the effective process of student assistance and is recurrent in the respondents' statements. When reporting the services provided by the municipality to meet the demands of goal 4 of the PME, L1 lists a series of services developed by different actors, in addition to partnerships established with the Municipal Department of Education.

The secretary today supports each place in different ways. [...] with concessions for people, with renting a house to operate some entities, school transport. [...] the State has a partnership, but the entities do not! And we guarantee school transport, with other support as well. Apart from the agreements that we establish. We support the Anjo Azul association, we support APAE, we support the Center (CEEEEC) and we support the Riding School because these 4 entities also do relevant work for the municipality, in addition to working in the network we support each one of them. They also, at times, have information that overlaps, our students are served by each entity. So, for the network, it is of fundamental importance that each entity does its job so that together we can guarantee the educational process of each child (L1).

If we analyze what was announced above more carefully, we will be able to consider the actions outlined there that provide structural support for events, transport, among others, which does not constitute, for us, a context of partnership for

the effective inclusion of students in common education. The institutions mentioned are Special Education, with services complementary to common education and not schooling. In view of this, we understand that the promotion of access for people with disabilities in the context of municipal schools has been offered in an incipient manner in different institutions without, however, being configured as an exclusive education policy for the network.

This statement can be confirmed by the response to the L4 questionnaire, when asked about the services provided by the municipality. The interviewee reaffirms the partnership mentioned above: “[...] in partnership with the State Center for Special Education of Caetité, as well as APAE, monitoring of students is carried out after regular school hours” (L4). In the case of the municipal network, services are offered in

[...] Multifunctional Resource rooms, which are environments equipped with equipment, furniture and teaching materials. In this room there is a specialized teacher to assist students, providing pedagogical support; when necessary, we have assistance from a health professional (psychologist, speech therapist, psychiatrist, etc.). [...] in this case, there are two that are activated, one in the Terezinha Bonfim Silva School Group and the other in the Dácio Oliveira School Group (L6).

This offer, limited to two resource rooms, with a professional in each room, is the only service in the network to promote student inclusion in regular education. The services mentioned above are not developed within the scope of municipal power, and their participation takes place as a supporter of the proposed activities, not in the dynamics of planning and articulation for the inclusive process.

When asked which actions would be a priority for 2019, question 11 (eleven) of the questionnaire, it is possible to see that L5 recognizes the need for an expansion of services that are directly linked to service in the network. For L5, service requires

[...] measures to better serve people with disabilities in the regular education network ensured by Law No. 13,146 Brazilian Inclusion Law and by goal 4 of the PNE, which ensures the education of the population from 4 (four) to 17 (seventeen) years with disabilities, global developmental disorders and high abilities and giftedness, measures that would offer bilingual education, in Brazilian Sign Language – LIBRAS to students with hearing impairments [...] (L5).

Regarding the same question, L4 believes that an important action would be “[...] training for the school community, for truly assertive ‘integration’ work”. L6 complements, listing a series of necessary services, including:

[...] training and training of teachers; expansion of the multidisciplinary team; Implementation of more AEE rooms; awareness and sensitization of Education Units to exercise their role; more effective support for non-governmental institutions; alignment of actions involving all entities, among others (L6).

The speakers of the questionnaire, L4, L5 and L6, are subjects directly linked to partner institutions and representatives of Special and Inclusive Education at the Municipal Education Forum. This place of speech translates, in this aspect, the absence of dialogue and a project that interconnects these actions for an effective response to the enunciators' propositions. It is noteworthy that the materialization of discourses on the universalization of inclusive education in the municipality of Caetité-BA is justified in a theoretical field that regulates knowledge about school inclusion and the mechanisms that make institutional discourse work; the latter, in the field of governmentality, places ‘continuum’ services as the first step towards an ordering, which brings together and makes a new way of doing politics work; what Foucault calls biopolitics, established by collective power over life, making control over previously dispersed elements more effective. According to Veiga-Neto (2001, p. 7), “[...] all of this means bringing these multiple heads closer together, including and ordering them in a new and increasingly larger and more nuanced field of knowledge”.

During the interview with L1, the question arose about what the pedagogical proposal for inclusive education in the municipality would be. In his response, L1 situates the context in which “[...] assumes (resumes) the Department of Education [...]” and assumes as an object of discussion “[...] precisely goal 4. Because this existed provocation, the need in the municipality for a different look at this clientele [...]” (L1). Defining goal 4 as the work plan for 2017, the actions focused, according to L2, on the perspective of inclusive education. This enunciator states that during this period the Guidelines for Special Education were created and this was sent for analysis and approval by the Municipal Education Council. L3 confirms approval of the Guidelines in 2018. These guidelines were not made available to us.

At this time, the secretariat provides a list of activities carried out over the period between 2017-2019, as shown in Table 3, where the actions implemented by the municipality are presented.

Chart 3 - Actions implemented by the municipality in the period 2017/2019

Formation of a Multidisciplinary Team:	Specialist teacher; Institutional and Clinical Psychopedagogue; Speech therapist; Psychologist; Libras interpreter; Escorts; Learning Mediators; Caregiver.
Multifunctional Resource Rooms	01 - Therezinha Bonfim Municipal School 02 - Dácio Alves Oliveira School Group
Inclusive Education in Movement Project	Workshops for guidance to the school community
Specialized Professional Intersectorality	Senador Ovídio Teixeira School Group Municipal Health and Social Action Secretary
Partnerships	Caetité State Center for Special Education; Blue Angel Association; Living and Overcoming Special Riding Center; Association of Parents and Friends of the Exceptional (APAE).
Accessibility	Physical structure of schools; Signaling in Libras; Training in Libras.
Training	Caregivers; Libras interpreters.
Continuing training in Inclusive Education	Attention deficit disorder and hyperactivity; Learning difficulties and disorders in the school context; Intellectual Deficit: Learning and Inclusion; Final meeting: Report of experiences.

Source: Municipal Department of Education SME/Caetité-Bahia (2019).

The actions listed in table 3 appear frequently in the speeches of L1 and L2, but are not mentioned by L3, as, when answering question 7 of the interview, he reveals that he is “unaware”, for example, of a continued training policy for educators who work in special education or in schools with inclusive students. The actions vaguely permeate L6's speech, which mentions the multifunctional rooms and the work of the multidisciplinary team and do not appear in the L4 and L5 questionnaires. In the case of continuing training in inclusive education, these occurred at different times, characterized by a monthly meeting.

This way, the discourses serve an institutionalized basis that will “[...] exert pressure and constraint on other discourses [...]” (Foucault, 2018, p. 04). We identify the exercise of power, which seeks to control, organize and redistribute discourses, in the materiality of actions that, in their positivity, seek to meet a firm commitment to include, through the production of new ways of knowing and doing and, as a consequence, builds new power relations within the inclusion process. At the same time, they reveal resistance as an effect of this power, glimpsed in discourses that do not recognize the actions measured in the institutional context. For Foucault, where there is power there is resistance, making it necessary to recognize the subjectivation character of subjects in power relations.

The activities proposed as actions for the implementation of goal 4 of the PME for the municipality of Caetité reveal themselves to be inconsistent in the context of schooling, given that the process of including the target audience of special education cannot be decontextualized from the daily life of the classroom. common class. Actions must imply changes in the teaching-learning process, propositions of new methodologies, curricular adaptations, so that they, in fact, correspond to the specific needs of each individual.

Final considerations

In the PME context, we identified the desire to expand access from the inclusive perspective of students with disabilities, global developmental disorders and high abilities/giftedness. This desire for truth is expressed in the strategies proposed in goal 4 of the PME in the municipality of Caetité, through the circulation of the discourse of expanding students' access to common education, through partnerships with services outside the municipal network, which support the provision of services compatible with physical, pedagogical access conditions, resources and language; these anchored in the concept of Inclusive Education with social quality and human rights.

The actions listed as implementation of the PME goal 4 strategies are arrangements that do not translate into an inclusion project in the context of common education. These are necessary services, relevant to specialized care, but they do not reflect a change in the educational context's stance that tends the discourse of difference to emerge actions, attitudes and conceptions that bring about new meanings in the normalizing action.

Given the speeches analyzed and the actions identified, the scientific discourse exposes the fragility of this construct of inclusive knowledge in the municipality of Caetité, since the guarantee of schooling in common education for the target audience of special education must consider actions that promote new pedagogical practices, in different learning contexts, knowledge socialization networks, teacher training to work in common education, causing significant changes in the school context that highlight the specific demands within the learning proposal for all.

Thus, in the analysis undertaken, we found, as proposed by Miranda and Galvão Filho (2011, p. 103), “[...] an acceptance of school inclusion, but the mechanisms used to ensure it is carried out effectively are not having success, as there are still no changes in the structural aspects, in the attitude of the subjects involved and in the pedagogical aspects [...]”. The fragility of the actions carried out and the discontinuity of inclusion services have a negative impact on the materialization of the strategies proposed in goal 4 of the PME to meet the demands of inclusive education for access, “universalization” and services for the target audience of special education, in teaching common in the municipality of Caetité.

References

BRASIL. **Lei nº 9.394/96, de 20 de dezembro de 1996.** Lei de Diretrizes e Bases da Educação. Brasília: Ministério da Educação e do Desporto, Secretaria de Educação Fundamental, 1996.

BRASIL. Presidência da República. Lei Brasileira de Inclusão da Pessoa com Deficiência - Lei nº 13.146. Brasília: Casa Civil. Subchefia para Assuntos Jurídicos, 2015. Disponível em: <http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_ato2015-2018/2015/lei/l13146.htm>. Acesso em: 12 jan. 2018.

CAETITÉ. Lei nº 789, de 22 de junho de 2015. Plano Municipal de Educação. **Diário Oficial do Município**, Caetité, BA, 23 jun. 2015. Ano 1- Edição nº 00085/Caderno 1, p. 18-198.

FOUCAULT, M. O sujeito e o poder. In: DREYFUS, H. L. **Michel Foucault: uma trajetória filosófica: (para além do estruturalismo e da hermenêutica)**. Rio de Janeiro: Forense Universitária, 1995. p. 231-249.

FOUCAULT, M. **Vigiar e punir: nascimento da prisão**. 38 ed. Petrópolis/RJ: Vozes, 2010.

FOUCAULT, M. **História da sexualidade 1: a vontade de saber**. 7 ed. Rio de Janeiro/São Paulo: Paz e Terra, 2018.

GARCIA, R. M. C. O conceito de flexibilidade curricular nas políticas públicas de inclusão escolar. In: JESUS, O. M.; BAPTISTA, C. B.; VICTOR, S. L. (Org.). **Inclusão, práticas pedagógicas e trajetórias de pesquisa**. Porto Alegre: Mediação, 2007. p. 15-33.

INEP. Instituto Nacional de Estudos e Pesquisas Educacionais Anísio Teixeira (INEP). **Censo Escolar, 2018**. Brasília: MEC, 2018.

MENDES, E. G.; VIRALONGA, C. A. R.; ZERBATO, A. P. **Ensino Colaborativo como apoio à inclusão escolar: unindo esforços entre educação comum e especial**. São Carlos: EduFSCar, 2014.

MIRANDA, T. G.; GALVÃO FILHO, T. A. (Org.). **Educação Especial em contexto inclusivo: reflexão e ação**. Salvador: EDUFBA, 2011.

RESENDE, H. (Org.). **Michel Foucault: a arte neoliberal de governar a educação**. São Paulo: Intermeios; Brasília: Capes/Cnpq, 2018.

SKLIAR, C. A invenção e a exclusão da alteridade deficiente a partir dos significados da normalidade. **Educação & Realidade**, v.24, n.1, 1987.

VEIGA-NETO, A. Incluir para saber. Saber para excluir. **Pro-posições**, v.12, n.2-3, 2001.